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Ethical Guidelines on Incentivizing and Fairly Rewarding Citizens Engaged in Open Innovation Pathways

D4.1

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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Executive Summary

In innovation contexts, where the final aim is to reach the market with new products, services, and processes for profit, how can we ensure that citizens' contributions to co-creation approaches can be adequately recognised and rewarded? What kind of options and mechanisms can innovation ecosystems adopt to incentivise citizen-led innovation for “societal alignment” (Kuzma et al., 2018) but also guarantee fair and transparent compensation for those who participate in the design or refinement of new marketable products?

MOSAIC pilots (in Milan and Gothenburg) will potentially lead to the identification of innovative ideas. Therefore, all stakeholders participating in this process must feel that the added value they bring to the identification of concrete solutions is valued and protected. Citizens are particularly vulnerable to unfair exploitation of their contributions. For this, and in continuity with T3.3, the focus of this deliverable is a multi-step approach implemented by Task leader FGB to create ethical guidelines to be used as a reference during the implementation of the pilots.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Form
EC	European Commission
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation

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Introduction

More and more, citizens are becoming critical actors in innovation pathways. From makerspaces to patient-innovator initiatives and data-collecting platforms, innovation pipelines have been transformed through ideas and creativity from engaged citizens. In doing so, citizens in meaningful collaboration for responsible innovation (Jarmai et al., 2020) are influential actors in the innovation ecosystem, thus shifting the economic dynamics as well as the relevance and ethos of new products and services. At the same time, critiques have been raised on the exploitation of grassroots initiatives and citizen science by innovation entrepreneurs, start-up impresarios, and venture capitalists, depicted as “the public donating its unpaid work and data to privately owned, online entities” and “an extension of the sharing economy into the heart of scientific research”.

In innovation contexts, where the final aim is to reach the market with new products, services, and processes for profit, how can we ensure that citizens’ contributions to co-creation approaches can be adequately recognised and rewarded? What kind of options and mechanisms can innovation ecosystems adopt to incentivise citizen-led innovation for “societal alignment” (Kuzma et al., 2018) but also guarantee fair and transparent compensation for those who participate in the design or refinements of new marketable products?

MOSAIC intends *co-creation* as “a form of collaborative innovation, which is initiated by one or more members of the Quadruple Helix (a company, citizens or citizen group, research organisation or public agency), and involves contributors or co-creators from the other "helices" but above all from civil society to co-produce tangible outcomes, such as technologies, services or new organisational structures”.

MOSAIC pilots (in Milan and Gothenburg) will potentially lead to the identification of innovative ideas. Therefore, all stakeholders participating in this process must feel that the added value they bring to the identification of concrete solutions is valued and protected. Citizens are particularly vulnerable to unfair exploitation of their contributions. For this, and in continuity with T3.3, the focus of this report is a multi-step approach implemented by Task leader FGB to create ethical guidelines to be used as a reference before and during the concretisation of the pilots. The guidelines included in this report will be helpful for any co-innovation process. Within the context of MOSAIC, the two pilot cities will adapt and set context-based and specific ethical guidelines before starting their co-creation processes, starting from the MOSAIC ethical guidelines.

MOSAIC research leading to the ethical guidelines

Fair rewarding citizens engaged in co-creation processes start by drawing a clear distinction between public and private interests and warranting transparency since the beginning of co-creation initiatives.

In the private sector, product ideation, testing, and refinement are founded on an apparent “pact” between companies testing their ideas and products and the participants who accept to share their habits and ideas with marketing researchers and, therefore, with product developers and their private companies. In this field, when participating in marketing research, potential or ideal consumers are rewarded with money (or vouchers and other goods, in some cases charity donations) for their time spent providing feedback through interviews, surveys or focus groups. Roles are transparent: for example, in Italy, participants are informed that they typically will receive a compensation of 5-6€ for answering a 30 minute questionnaire and 25-30€ for participating in a 2-hours focus group. These amounts can change according to specific country standards. In this type of research, crucial is the role of recruiters. These professionals are in charge of and authorised to collect data from people in specific geographical areas; consumers provide their availability to be contacted if they meet the recruitment criteria and then take part in marketing analysis processes.

In public interest initiatives, the motivation lies in the principle of solidarity. The aim of involving citizens (seen in this case as individuals with a set of social and political rights and duties rather than individuals who consume goods and services provided by a producer or provider) is to contribute to creating, changing, enhancing, and defending common goods. Public actors see the possibility (and, in some cases, the duty) of contributing to something positive for the community as the primary reward to citizens for donating their time and ideas. In fact, community-oriented forms of compensation are preferable for public administrations. Rewarding citizens' contributions in ways that benefit the collectivity rather than individuals is seen as a fairer way of rewarding engagement while benefitting the public good. This is also often seen by citizens as a strong source of motivation: knowing that their participation will bring substantial amelioration to them and those around them is often mentioned as a key expected outcome. On the contrary, a lack of feedback and tangible results leads to disappointment and frustration.

What happens in public-private initiatives, such as the co-creation processes implemented in MOSAIC, which are typically needed in Mission-like settings where shared ideas are crucial to overcoming complex challenges? How can citizens be rewarded, and what kind of fair process can be set up and implemented to ensure that no unfair exploitation will occur?

Research Objectives and tools

In order to define ethical guidelines for fair citizens' engagement in open innovation that could be useful for cities enrolled in the EU Cities Mission, MOSAIC set three main research objectives:

1. to explore the meanings of co-creation as the basis for understanding different innovation contexts while assessing whether they provide any approach to fair rewarding of participants

2. to understand what are the rewarding strategies currently used in co-creation experiences and how to improve them
3. Understand how fair rewards can be assessed and who should be responsible for that when setting up co-creation processes.

A preliminary review of existing reports and documents was carried out in T3.3, covering citizen engagement best practices. The review, corroborated by the results emerging from the co-creation review performed in T2.1, showed that the issue of fair rewarding is widely overlooked by practitioners and scholars, not only in the Mission context but also more in general in co-innovation settings, as MOSAIC has intuited since the beginning (this was spotted as one of the SwafS gaps to be filled) (Robinson, Simone and Mazzonetto, 2020). Thus, the review did not allow for gathering valuable input. It has highlighted how a wide diversity of approaches have been used in the past to reward citizens who engage with research and innovation processes led by the public sector. On the contrary, rewarding mechanisms found in literature in situations involving both the public and private sector (industries), such as co-innovation in the Mission context, are almost non-existent. These are mainly traceable in the Health sector, which is quite far, in terms of types of stakeholders and innovation ecosystem dynamics and rules, from the context explored in MOSAIC. For this, to understand if and how this issue is perceived by the cities involved in the Climate neutral and smart cities Mission, structured interviews with city representatives from the 8 cities (MOSAIC pilots and replicators) were conducted in the months June-July 2022.

The results that emerged, collated with further outcomes of T3.1 and T3.2, have been used to elaborate a set of policy recommendations, which was finally produced in the shape of a policy brief to support MOSAIC cities and beyond in the fair implementation of co-innovation pathways.

The MOSAIC policy brief was presented and discussed in an online workshop with representatives of pilot and replicator cities held in November 2022. The workshop aimed to identify solutions and mechanisms that open innovation ecosystems can adopt to incentivise but also guarantee fair and transparent compensation for citizens who participate in the design or refinement of new marketable products.

During the workshop, participants were also presented with and discussed preliminary results from a survey run by FGB on relevant elements for proper ethical guidelines, addressed to quadruple-helix stakeholders and the active community around the topic of climate-neutral smart cities and co-innovation across Europe. The survey was publicly launched in October and promoted via multiple channels (MOSAIC and partners' channels such as websites, social media, networks, direct mailing, and the project newsletters). The survey collected responses until the end of November 2022.

To summarise, in order to investigate the topic of fair rewards in co-creation experiences, MOSAIC deployed the following set of research tools.

1. 8 structured interviews with cities' representatives involved in the EU Cities Mission (guidelines used to facilitate the interviews are available in Annex 1).

The main topics covered were:

- a) the role of citizens in co-creation processes
 - b) the concept of fair rewarding of citizens
 - c) why is rewarding important
 - d) how can citizens be fairly rewarded
 - e) who should guarantee that citizens' are fairly rewarded in co-creation processes
 - f) who should assess if rewarding mechanisms are balanced with citizens' contributions and how.
2. Responses to the MOSAIC survey. The structure of the survey is available in Annex 2;
 3. Results of the online workshop held in November. The Padlet collecting the 14 participants' contributions to the discussion is available in Annex 3.

The analysis of the resulting texts (transcriptions of interviews, contributions during the workshop and written answers resulting from the survey) was supported by the software ATLAS.ti, a text mining tool that allows the label of texts according to thematic codes “negotiated” by the analysts on the base of the research objectives. Adding codes to the text portions results in researchers re-discussing the interpretation of the interviewees’ answers until the coding process is concluded.

From an initial set of 31 codes, the process resulted in the selection of 13 codes, clustered into four main groups according to the research objectives: shared meanings of co-creation; reasons to participate and reward; tools of rewarding; assessment.

Interviewees, respondents of the open-ended questionnaire and participants in the workshop were primarily civil servants in public administrations, researchers in the field of social studies of science and technology, and facilitators in knowledge transfer in R2B-B2B.

In the following section, all the participants in the 3 phases of the research are referred to as “respondents”. All texts in italics are quotes from respondents' answers.

Results

Shared meanings of co-creation

One of the main findings from the analysis and already discussed in the MOSAIC Policy Brief is the lack of a unique and shared definition of co-creation. It is often the case that types of citizen engagement approaches are used as synonyms of co-creation (e.g., co-design, consultations, public engagement, etc.) at various institutional levels. As explained above, the MOSAIC co-creation definition sees citizens as central actors in co-creation processes, in which tangible outcomes are co-produced collaboratively. Co-creation is a peculiar and specific method to involve citizens, which needs to be distinguished from other forms of participation, that can co-exist with and enhance co-creation. Co-creation aims to solve together a specific problem, finding suitable solutions that are beneficial for all.

Citizens' views, experiences, ideas, and even data are central to identifying challenges (citizens as co-designers), elaborating answers (citizens as co-creators), and monitoring their effects and impacts (citizens as co-evaluators).

Co-creation is not a straightforward concept. It overlaps with other forms of citizen engagement.

There is a scarce experience on the ground of co-innovation.

Secondly, more and more citizens are becoming critical actors in innovation pathways, actively contributing as innovators by sharing ideas, knowledge, or even personal data. Since the participation of citizens in co-creation activities is essential, citizens' contributions should be properly and fairly acknowledged and rewarded, especially in processes where the aim is to bring new products, services and processes to the market to generate profits. Whilst several examples can be found of experiences and reflections on mechanisms to compensate citizens' efforts in public deliberations for policy making (such as Citizens' Jury, Citizens' Assembly, Consensus Conference, etc.), the topic is relatively new in the realm of citizen engagement in Open Innovation settings. Depending on the type of contribution they bring to the process, a solid framework is needed to reward citizens' efforts equitably, and moving beyond monetary compensation (also beyond money but adopting a fair approach) is required.

Reasons to participate and fairly reward

According to the analysis, when sharing ideas and dedicating time to co-creation activities, citizens can play a key role in the following:

Participating in the development of services

Sharing their data

Interpreting data

Sharing their experiences and needs

Advocating for rights and demands while taking part in joint enterprises of co-creation

Wide spreading the results of co-creation activities

Although citizens' contribution is fundamental for planning, designing and developing products and services, their participation is generally perceived as something that should be done for free in the name of a solidarity principle, the so-called *norm of reciprocity* (Jackson P. M., 2021). Rewards seem advisable only to compensate for citizens' time and dedication when participating in co-creation meetings and events, but not for exploiting co-created products/services.

Ideally, intellectual property rights, as well as all the benefits deriving from processes of co-creation, should be adequately distributed among contributors, including the citizens who took part in meetings sharing their knowledge, practice, and creative endeavours.

However, citizens are particularly vulnerable to unfair exploitation of their contribution, especially in processes where outcomes could be brought to the market in the form of profitable new products, services, or processes.

Motivations/advantages for citizens

Two main motivation factors of citizens' participation emerge from the analysis.

Empowerment:

People can create something; thus, they are part of something which is real.

Advocacy:

Citizens participate in developing services meant for them, services they need and use.

Citizens want to express their needs and ask for direct collaboration with us.

Respondents are also aware that these two motivations are often not seen nor shared by citizens, who feel disconnected from the cultural, political and economic environment where they live, work, and study. This results in reasons *not to* participate and, from the point of view of co-creation processes' organisers, it leads to unsuccessful recruiting. Only the so-called "usual suspects" often participate, generating frustration because of scarce participation.

To prevent this, one of the respondents suggests fostering an "anticipatory attitude" in those who set up co-creation activities - they should investigate the needs of citizens *before* and not *after* the process:

The idea of providing rewarding mechanisms is excellent, though citizens' needs should be at the centre from the very beginning rather than at the end of the discussion. They should also intervene in design, not just take part in the final part – when the solutions are already there. This requires assessing case by case based on the citizens' requests.

Moreover, a fair reward is also seen as connected to the type of benefit that is expected:

It depends on how much citizens get out of it directly - for example, a commercial solution with limited benefit for the participant vs a very local solution that improves the participant's everyday life.

Obstacles in fair rewarding

The “feeling of not being listened to” appears as one of the main frustrations for citizens and other stakeholders involved in co-creation processes.

Initiators of co-creation processes should be reminded of the importance of informing co-producers (i.e. all stakeholders involved) of realistic potential uptakes of the co-creation outcomes, both at the start and end of the process. Providing clear and transparent information is seen as a form of reward and a key priority for all respondents.

Respondents also highlighted two critical obstacles to fairly acknowledging stakeholders in open innovation processes led by public administrations: administrative on one side and equality-related on the other.

MOSAIC researcher: Would re-distribution of results of co-creation be possible?

Respondent: Definitely not, we should activate public procedures ... Also, releasing data related to citizens to any company is not possible, as it would mean offering an economic advantage to a company, in particular, to an industry instead of another.

MOSAIC researcher: Do you, as a public authority, adopt some forms of distribution of the benefits coming out of co-creation activities?

Respondent: This is not really possible, it would imply starting administrative procedures related to IPR and data transfer from citizens to companies, for example. This would end in favoring a company instead of others. An example is an app developed by an Italian Municipality, where a co-creation exercise took to the promotion of the app developed by a company. This was considered inappropriate given the dimension of the process, promoted by the public administration but exploited by a private company.

Fair rewarding tools

Based on respondents' suggestions regarding what can be adopted or implemented by a public administration, the analysis led to the identification of four main groups of fair rewarding tools: a sense

of ownership/social recognition, free use of products and services, material rewards, and shareholding.

Some respondents also highlighted the need to directly ask co-creation participants (i.e. citizens and other stakeholders) about what they envisage as benefits for them in such processes:

[We] researchers tend to imply what citizens want or how they can be rewarded, but citizens can have very good ideas on how a citizen's budget can be used or invested for their own benefit.

Ask citizens what compensation would be adequate.

Some respondents also pointed out the need to clearly define the ownership and compensation mechanisms of co-creation outcomes from the very start of the process:

The rules and outcomes should be outlined before the process occurs, namely, declaring who has ownership.

Citizens should be able to participate based on their assessment of the value of their contributions and how they are compensated.

A further proposition was to allocate a dedicated budget *in advance* when planning the co-creation process:

I think that is a difficult issue, but perhaps a good starting point would be to establish a percentage of funding to be used for the citizens as co-creators rather than by the researchers or the companies.

A challenge identified by one of our respondents is the assumption of responsibility after the process of co-creation:

Would the responsibility need to shift to the owners of exploitable results?

- *Social recognition*

Without claiming any representative status of our qualitative research design, the words “recognition” and “recognise” are among the most recurrent in our transcripts database when associated with “reward/rewarding”. Recognition is intended to ensure co-creators visibility.

Civil servants, above all, seem to support the idea that “fair rewards” are, for example, the possibility for stakeholders to be recognised for their participation in such processes by being mentioned in public documents or to make new contacts and be seen in their community:

[Our proposed reward] is to recognise the [stakeholders’] contribution ensuring a lively interaction with them, talking as a collective “we”.

We must recognise their contribution.

Recognition of inputs by acknowledging names in outputs and on products.

They can grow their own network and meet new people from their area.

We should recognise people who participated, especially in case they don’t have the right to earn through their ideas.

The case of hackathons for co-creation is frequently mentioned, in which visibility and public recognition seem to be a relevant feature of fair reward:

In hackathons, when the winner sees that their idea is successful and a company is interested in it, we feel it’s also a good motivation.

In some hackathons, the winner gets money and to further develop an idea with a company. We don’t know how the rights ownership went, but we know they got a recognition of being the winners.

As a student, showcasing ideas that can raise interest from professionals is already a big reward.

- *Free usage of products and services*

The second group of fair rewarding propositions focuses on the free use of products and services deriving from co-creation pathways.

Free access to new products/services developed through co-creation... Something that can help in their lives, or the possibility to use the product for free for some time.

Moreover, allowing the co-creators to access any data generated through their collaborative effort is considered fair.

- *Material rewards*

We can give intangible goods, such as museum or events tickets.

We will prefer to focus on giving good food, a special place, a celebrity to talk to, rather than gift cards or material products.

... Giving special access to city properties.

Vouchers, coupons and monetary compensation are mentioned by respondents. These are often presented as something that should ideally benefit the community or the neighbourhood.

From my own experience working with communities in rural villages in Cornwall , a group of citizens I worked with wanted a projector and a screen for their community centre so they could perform better activities and even rent them to get some extra income for the community centre.

We have also tried some lotteries, not to give a gift to everyone participating but only a few winners.

Therefore, an alternative to material objects is to reward the co-creators before and while participating by reimbursing public transport tickets and babysitting, and providing (sustainable) food.

We gave participants food, childcare and gifts, but it turned out not to be good as it is a grey area in terms of taxation. We therefore opted gift cards.

To be fair, we have to remember the climate perspective, to make the reward as climate-friendly as possible - using for example, vouchers for vegetarian meals.

Food as a complement to monetary compensation - citizens' time is valuable and thinking about how you could make it as easy as possible for them to participate, you can think in timing and including, for example, a dinner.

Since most of the respondents are civil servants, they stressed the importance of motivation more than material rewards:

Gifts are not key, people have been more motivated by the subject.

Public administrations struggle with finding ways to provide forms of reward that move beyond material compensation for time dedication. While they acknowledge the importance of recognising all stakeholders' contributions, they also need this recognition to comply with public regulations.

- *Shareholding*

Out of all suggestions, sharing profits is likely the fairest of all propositions collected, especially in the case of co-creation outcomes that become profitable products or services.

However, this option is just mentioned as ideal, and respondents don't report any substantial experience with it. An open question remains on *how* to share intellectual property and profits.

The creative commons seems, at the moment, the most likely solution:

Co-creation should be a creative commons way of working.

Assessment

When asked about how to assess whether citizens' participation in Open Innovation processes is fair, respondents highlighted the need to contextualise the co-creation activity before setting up the assessment procedure:

It depends on how much citizens get out of it directly - for example, a commercial solution with limited benefit for the participant is very different from a very local solution that improves the participants' everyday life.

- *Assessment of responsibilities*

Respondents provided three types of answers to the question, "Who is responsible for the assessment so that a fair reward is ensured to co-creators?"

On one side, the initiators of the co-creation should be in charge of its assessment, in their role of leaders and sometimes funders of the process. Ideally, they should define an assessment framework during the planning phase of the process and recruit an external expert to conduct or support the evaluation.

[The entity/actors in charge of assessing that the reward for co-creators is fair should be:]

The organisation promotes the co-creation process.

The organisers of the co-creation process through surveys or interviews.

Those implementing spaces of co-creation: researchers, developers but also the policy level.

The municipality or an assigned agency.

The government of the agency who initiated the co-creation process.

Funding bodies.

Expert advisors of the funding body, or independent panels of advisors.

Interesting suggestions also emerged regarding the monitoring and sharing of co-creation outcomes with the participants once the process is over:

First they make agreements at the start and then an independent third party will assess them ethically and then monitor whether agreements are met.

Project funding agencies should demand reporting also beyond a project, regarding the return of co-created results to participants.

A different perspective is that citizens should be the principal evaluators of the co-creation:

Citizen expert panels should evaluate, not just expert panels.

The third point of view is that sharing responsibility could be the solution:

Everybody in the co-creation partnership is responsible for the assessment.

A committee composed of the citizens and the process promoters.

Ethical Guidelines

Relying both on the research conducted and experiences, constraints and needs from co-creation processes initiators (mainly local authorities and municipalities) described before, here following a list of elements to be considered as “ethical guidelines” to be taken into account before planning, setting and implementing a co-innovation pathway.

- No co-creation process should be set up without a prior shared reflection on intellectual property rights and the potential profits distribution of its outputs. Especially in negotiating with private sector representatives their participation in the process, this element should be highlighted and discussed before the start of the co-creation path. The involvement of the private sector in co-creation processes represents both a challenge (e.g. in case of unfair appropriation of shared ideas) and an opportunity. Having representatives of the private sector involved from the start should be mediated by co-creation initiators by fostering an open conversation on potential rewards that can be acceptable to them.
- The definition of intellectual property rights and potential profits distribution can be achieved through a top-down process (i.e. the public administration running the processes defines and informs participants about what is achievable and whom it belongs to) or, even better, a bottom-up approach (i.e. all participants are involved in the definition of rewarding expectations, ahead of the start of the process).
- Public administrations often dispose of entire units/departments dedicated to managing and strengthening the collaboration with (and governance of) the private sector. It is advisable to involve representatives of such offices in co-creation processes. They can both support the exploitation of co-creation ideas through city-owned channels (e.g. business incubators) and mediate discussions on ownership issues with private companies involved in the process. With them, while looking at sectors in which this kind of discussion is gaining momentum (open data), explore a new way of reconfiguring products and services for the public good as “public products”, focusing less on who are the idea/products conception holders and more on the purposes for which the product can be used.
- Creative commons forms of ownership are ideal, even though only sometimes possible. Shared ownership of outcomes should always be preferred. When not possible, due to the need to privatise innovative ideas, other forms of reward should be adopted, such for example shareholding or free access to products and services for those who contributed to their development.
- Transparency is key. Whether any form of reward is considered or not, it is important to inform participants from the start about the conditions of their participation in the process. This should be clearly stated in informed consent forms and explained to them.

- Communication actions to inform co-creation participants on how their contribution has been used and finalised is of utmost importance. While planning a co-creation process, define means and channels for follow-up activities.

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Annex 1 - Guidelines for structured interviews with cities

(other questions not related to fair reward)

CITIZENS' MOTIVATION AND FAIRNESS OF CO-CREATION PROCESSES (ACCORDING TO THE CITIES)

CITIZENS MOTIVATION FOR TAKING PART IN CO-CREATION

- What could foster citizen participation in co-creation processes?
- What could prevent citizen participation in co-creation processes?
- How can citizens contribute to co-creation processes according to your experience?

ONLY IN CASE OF MOSAIC-LIKE CO-CREATION:

- Are the contributions from citizens fairly recognized and rewarded?
- If yes, how?
- If not, what could be improved?

FAIRNESS

- What kind of fair rewards/incentives to citizens taking part in the co-creation process could be provided?
- What kind of fair rewards/incentives to other actors taking part in the co-creation process could be provided?
- What other factors need to be considered to make the co-creation process fair in your opinion?

(other questions not related to fair reward)

Annex 2 - Call for suggestions on fair citizens' rewarding in co-creation

This call for suggestions is part of the research activities of MOSAIC, a EU H2020 funded project aimed to promote co-creation approaches in the realm of the EU Mission "Climate-neutral and smart cities".

Co-creation

Co-creation is “a form of collaborative innovation, which is initiated by one or more members of the Quadruple Helix (a company, citizens or citizen group, research organisation or public agency), and involves contributors or co-creators from the other "helices" but above all from civil society to co-produce tangible outcomes, such as technologies, services or new organizational structures”. Other valuable citizens’ engagement approaches (e.g., public deliberation for policy making, consultations, etc.) are out of the scope of this call for suggestions.

Citizens’ role and rewarding in co-creation

More and more citizens are becoming key actors in innovation pathways and the engagement of citizens is often encouraged at different institutional level as one of the most powerful tools to render innovation more responsible and responsive to societal needs.

Also thanks to key enabling technologies (e.g., digital devices and platforms, 3D printers, distribute renewable energy technologies), citizens becomes co-authors of innovation (e.g., new products developed with citizen-innovators, urban mobility applications based on citizens data).

However, despite their key role in co-creation in open innovation - where the final result could be reaching the market with new products, services and processes for profit, citizens are particularly vulnerable to unfair exploitation of their contribution.

How ensuring that citizens’ contributions in co-creation approaches can be properly recognized and rewarded?

What kind of options and mechanisms can innovation ecosystems adopt to incentivize citizens buy-in in collaborative innovation processes but also to guarantee a fair and transparent.

The call for suggestions

This call for suggestions is open to all actors from the quadruple helix from October 25th to November 25th.

Please share it with your contacts that can be willing and interested in taking part in this survey. Results will be published and used for further actions in MOSAIC and will be communicated on MOSAIC social media channels and website. Thank you!

*Mandatory field

GENERAL INFORMATION

1. Sector of your organization *

Business/industry

Civil Society/Citizens' groups

Research organization

Public agency/Pubic sector Other

2. Where is your organization from? (Country - and if applicable - Municipality and/or Region)

3. What is the core aim of your organization? (in short)

4. Has your organization ever contributed to co-creation processes? *

Yes, as organizer of the process

Yes, as initiators of the process

Yes, as participants

No

SHARING IDEAS AND EXPERIENCES ON FAIR CO-CREATION

5. How can citizens contribute to co-creation processes? (multiple choice) *

Sharing their ideas and creativity

Sharing their experiences and needs

Sharing their data

Other

6. If the answer was "other", please further explain.

7. How much do you think it is important to fairly reward citizens contributing to co-creation on a scale from 1 (minimum) to 5 (maximum)?

1 2 3 4 5

8. What is the main reason to find new mechanisms for citizens' rewarding in co-creation processes? (multiple choice)

To guarantee that the benefits of co-creation are equally distributed

To guarantee that citizens' efforts are properly recognized and compensated To guarantee the inclusivity of the process

To avoid unfair exploitation of citizens' contributions To increase the transparency of the entire process

To incentivize citizens' participation also in future processes

Other

9. How much do you think that citizens' taking part to co-creation processes are currently fairly rewarded on a scale from 1 (minimum) to 5 (maximum)?

1 2 3 4 5

10. How can citizens' efforts and contributions be fairly rewarded? (multiple choice) *

Monetary compensation Vouchers/Coupons

Sharing of profits when the outcomes of co-creation are on the market Free access to new product/services developed through co-creation Free access to other services

Other:

11. If the answer was "other" or if you have any additional comment, please share here yo ideas.

12. How citizens' efforts and contributions can be fairly rewarded? Please, share experiences and case studies in the field through short descriptions, keywords and possible links.

13. Who should guarantee that citizens' are fairly rewarded in co-creation processes?

14. Who should assess if rewarding mechanisms are balanced to citizens' contributions and how?

15. Any other comment that you would like to share

CONTACTS

If you would you like to be updated about MOSAIC results, please, provide your email address.

Thank you!

Annex 3 - Padlet from the online MOSAIC workshop on Fair Rewarding in Co-creation activities (November 9th, 2022)

